

Architectural Education in Rural Areas – An Overview

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ABSTRACT

Architecture has been in practice since man started creating a roof over his head for seeking protection from the weather. The nature of accommodation went on altering with the arrival of technology, the advance of new materials, shifting economic and social environment, growing. However, despite the fact architecture, which was practiced for a number of centuries in India, got recognition as a profession only recently. In this research paper on the bases of group discussion, survey and literature review an effort in understanding the need and objective of Architectural education in rural regions and explores the role of architects in rural Architecture education has been carried out.

Keywords: Rural Education, Architectural Education, Architectural College

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Architecture is known to be a combination of an art and science with operational field revolving around creating state of the art built environment to serve the basic human needs of living, working and care of mind and spirits besides circulation.. It is a unique blend of aesthetic, technology and humanities duly supported by technical input. The major objective of the paper is to study Architectural education in reference to the rural context. The author aims to explore major Challenges facing by Architectural education in rural areas. [1]

still the majority sections of rural areas lacks in basic substructure needs and a big loophole in the architectural education in rural areas.

1.2. Study Objective

1. To understand the challenges faced by Architectural education in rural areas.
2. To study the role of architects in rural Architecture education.

2. Literature Review

➤ Redefining the Role of Architects in the Rural Development

In this research paper author observed that the architects always limit their services to the wealthy and powerful people from urban areas. But the truth is that, it is the poor from the villages who need his services. His main duty is to try to preserve, improve and create the required quality of the built environment for the users towards the creation of a sustainable world. [2]

Author studied the role of architect and explores the various dimensions that can be added to his existing role with reference to the rural context. The author conducted group discussions and surveys to gather the relevant data to explore the opinions on the role of architects.

➤ Global Cultures and Architecture Education: The Case of the India Initiative

In this research paper authr tried to find the answers to questions like, how is architectural education enriched by

Figure No.1: Basic Comparison between architectural education in urban and rural areas

1.1. Problem Statement

In India people living in urban areas are about 33% of people still live in rural areas. India has sighted an exponential growth in the Architectural education in urban areas, but

the seemingly peripheral voices of diverse global cultures. How does the process of creating designs propositions within unfamiliar cultures and sites unknown encourages students to question their own assumptions and methods. [3]

➤ **Trends of Change and Alternative Models of Existence of Architectural Education**

As per author, rapid globalization, fluctuating market economy and deteriorating social and climatic conditions has made their imprint on the profession, practice and education in architecture. In academics compounding problems of lack of qualified faculty members, research and almost no participation of industry. Educational institutions are required to impart appropriate education that emphasizes 'learning and empowerment, over teaching' in graduates. [4]

➤ **Emerging Challenges And Issues In Architectural Education In India**

In this research paper author explores the rapid growth of institutions, architectural education is facing large number of

challenges and issues in terms of quality of education imparted; availability of quality faculty, mushrooming of architectural institutions, widening gap between education and profession, challenges posed by globalization and liberalization, changing architectural vocabulary, norms and standards of architectural education and new building materials & construction technologies besides role of the regulatory authorities. [1].

➤ **Present Scenario of Architecture Education In India**

In this paper author takes an overview of the present scenario of Architectural Education in India. Author provided some solution as per the overall study, in order to bridging the gap between the growing demand and supply of Architects. All architecture education and the new ones opening nowadays to have a check by COA so as to improve the quality of education. Architectural education can address two main issues a) understanding ourselves and b) to understand the emerging technologies and their implications on architectural design. [5]

3. Methodology

The Primary data will be obtained from group discussion & survey and secondary data will be composed based on literature review and correlated with the present investigation.

Figure No2: Overall Methodology Process

Table No.1: Participant involved a study and method of approach

Sr. No.	Participant	Method of Approach
1.	Faculty of Shri S D Patil College of Architecture, Islampur	Group Discussion
2.	Students of Architecture College	Group Discussion & Telephonic Discussion
3.	People from Architecture and Related Fields	Survey
4.	People from Rural Areas	Survey

4. Data Collection and Interpretation

The group discussion and survey as follows

Table No.2: Summary of Survey with Participant I: Faculty of Shri S D Patil College of Architecture

Sr. No.	Question	Opinion
1.	Current Scenario of Architectural education in Rural Areas	Poor – 30%, Avg. – 60% , Good – 10%
2.	Circumstance of basic needs facilitated in Urban and Rural Areas	Urban- Good, Rural – Poor to Avg.
3.	Percentage of Architects providing their services in Rural areas in the proportion of the population.	Rural < 30%, Urban > 95%
4.	How many are interested to provide their services in future.	Yes - 60%, No - 5%, May or May not be - 35%
5.	Factors which can influence the rural Architecture education.	Economy, Govt. Support, Infrastructure setup.

6.	Developing Production/Manufacturing Industries and Service Industry in Rural area can influence rural education and if yes, how many times the development can be expected.	Yes – 100 %, 2 -3 times of current growth.
7.	Is good health is the influential factor in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor -95%, May or May not be – 5%, Mean Scale - 7
8.	Is Affordability of education is the influential factor, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor – 100%, Mean Scale – 9.5
9.	Is Government can play an important role in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes, very important role – 90%, Yes important role – 10%, Mean Scale – 9.75
10.	What is the Awareness of Architectural education in rural areas?	Low – 70%, Medium – 30%, High - Nil
11.	Any way to make rural education more attractive or tending to Urban population.	Affordability, Good Infrastructure facility, Eco friendly environment, branded college, high standard of education facility
12.	What factors can influence you to choose work in the rural education sector.	Basic infrastructure facility, Decent pay, good transportation facility

Table No. 3: Summary of Survey with Participant II: Students of Architecture College

Sr. No.	Question	Opinion
1.	Current Scenario of Architectural education in Rural Areas	Poor – 45%, Avg. – 50%, Good – 05%
2.	Circumstance of basic needs facilitated in Urban and Rural Areas	Urban– Good, Rural – Poor
3.	How many are interested to provide their services in future.	Yes - 55%, May or May not be – 45%
4.	Factors can influence the rural Architecture education.	Affordable fees, Good faculty, Infrastructure setup, branded college, increasing awareness.
5.	Developing Production/Manufacturing Industries and Service Industry in Rural area can influence rural education and if yes, how much times the development can be expected.	Yes – 95 %, May or may not be – 5%, 1 -3 times of current growth.
6.	Is good health is the influential factor in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor -90%, May or May not be – 5%, No -5%, Mean Scale – 6.5
7.	Is Affordability of education is the influential factor, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor – 100%, Mean Scale – 8.5
8.	Is Government can play an important role in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes, very important role – 90%, Yes important role – 10%, Mean Scale – 9
9.	What is the Awareness of Architectural education in rural areas?	Low – 60%, Medium – 35%, High – 5%
10.	Any way to make rural education more attractive or tending to Urban population.	Affordability, Good Infrastructure facility, Environment friendly campus, Autonomous college, good education facility, Entertainment facility nearby campus.

Table No.4: Summary of Survey with Participant III: People from Architecture and Related Fields

Sr. No.	Question	Opinion
1.	Current Scenario of Architectural education in Rural Areas	Poor – 60%, Avg. – 25%, Good – 15%
2.	Circumstance of basic needs facilitated in Urban and Rural Areas	Urban– Good, Rural –Avg.
3.	Percentage of Architects providing their services in Rural areas in the proportion of the population.	Rural < 50%, Urban > 90
4.	How many are interested to provide their services in future.	Yes - 50%, No – 10%, May or May not be – 40%
5.	Factors can influence the rural Architecture education.	Monetary help by Govt., Infrastructure setup.
6.	Developing Production/Manufacturing Industries and Service Industry in Rural area can influence rural education and if yes, how much time the development can be expected.	Yes – 70-80 %, 2 times of current growth.
7.	Is good health is the influential factor in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor -90%, May or May not be – 10%, Mean Scale - 6

8.	Is Affordability of education is the influential factor, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor – 100%, Mean Scale – 10
9.	Is Government can play an important role in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes, very important role – 80%, Yes important role – 20%, Mean Scale – 9.5
10.	What is the Awareness of Architectural education in rural areas?	Low – 45-50%, Medium – 35-40%, High – 10-20%
11.	Any way to make rural education more attractive or tending to Urban population.	Affordability, Good Infrastructure facility

Table No.5: Summary of Survey with Participant IV: People from Rural Areas

Sr. No.	Question	Opinion
1.	Current Scenario of Architectural education in Rural Areas	Poor – 70%, Avg. – 20%, Good – 10%
2.	Circumstance of basic needs facilitated in Urban and Rural Areas	Urban– Good, Rural – Poor
3.	Factors which can influence the rural Architecture education.	Industry growth, Increase in rural population.
4.	Developing Production/Manufacturing Industries and Service Industry in Rural area can influence rural education and if yes, how much time the development can be expected.	Yes – 100 %, 2 -3 times of current growth.
5.	Is good health is the influential factor in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor -85%, May or May not be – 15%, Mean Scale – 7.5
6.	Is Affordability of education is the influential factor, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes influential factor – 100%, Mean Scale – 9.5
7.	Is Government can play an important role in rural education, if yes, how much you will rate them in the scale of 0 -10.	Yes, very important role – 95%, Yes important role – 05%, Mean Scale – 9
8.	What is the Awareness of Architectural education in rural areas?	Low – 70%, Medium – 30%, High - Nil
9.	Any way to make rural education more attractive or tending to Urban population.	Good faculty, Transparent system, discipline on campus

4.5. Interpretation of Survey

The comprehensive learning from the survey is simply presented in an illustrated format as below

Figure No. 3: Interpretation of Survey in bubble diagram

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Role of Architects and the profession of architecture assumes importance to create a sustainable built environment. With liberalization of technical education in India and large number of students opting for architecture as a career, a number of institutions imparting architectural education have increased manifold. With the rapid growth of

institutions, architectural education is facing a large number of challenges and issues especially in rural areas. On the bases of survey and group discussions are carried out following are the recommendations as follows.

Recommendation:

- Grant/Support from Government: As in the case of industrial sector, the government provides five year tax relief to the industries those who are establishing the industry in rural areas, comparable kind of grant is also expected to rural Architect institutes.
- Provoke Self-sustainable model in the planning stage: Planning of educational setup near to the planned SEZ/Industrial corridor/Industrial area which will backing each other. (Architecture College provides planning and construction consultancy to the industry with involving the students and students gets exposure of industry and site visits).
- Involving the local level institution and restructure them to facilitate the objective. Example Involving Gram Panchayat, NGO (Non-Government Organization), SHG (Self Help Group) and with the help of them improve the basic infrastructure set up and awareness of education.
- Smart village concept: Developing the village into a self-sustainable village and making it smarter village which will not only provide the basic infrastructure, but also facilitate the facility of lectures through video conferencing, high net speed to explore online learning platforms.

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